

Summary

While undertaking new research using data published as part of the Report “Worldwide evidence of a unimodal relationship between productivity and plant species richness”, it was discovered that the biomass data associated with one of the network’s 157 eight-by-eight meter sampling grids was mistakenly duplicated. Specifically, the sixty-four individual (1m²) biomass measurements associated with grid #138 were mistakenly duplicated from those of grid #137. Both of these sample grids were located in New Zealand. The corrected dataset will be made available on Dryad at the original location (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.038q8>). Using the corrected data, and the R scripts that were archived on Dryad at the time of publication, co-author J.P. repeated all analyses conducted in the original study. These analyses did not change any of the study’s conclusions, and yielded only minor changes to the results.